

Original Research

Should Firms Care More About Their Own Customers or All Consumers?

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Abstract

This study compares two strategic approaches, Customer Orientation (CO) and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), within the Cournot competition framework, in which firms strategically determine output quantities. The central question is whether firms prefer to focus on their own customers only (CO) or expand their purview to include all consumers (CSR). To address this issue, the study constructs and analyzes a two-stage game with linear inverse demand in which two firms compete. In the first stage, each firm simultaneously selects the optimal level for its corporate culture, specifically regarding CO and CSR. In the second stage, each firm simultaneously determines its output level to maximize its objective function. The equilibrium analysis reveals that when the two firms are symmetric, they ultimately care only about their own customers, thereby favoring CO over CSR. This outcome underscores the strategic dominance of CO in a Cournot duopoly competition with linear inverse demand. This suggests that when firms make quantity-setting decisions, they prioritize direct customer relationships over broader social responsibility. The findings contribute to the literature on industrial organization and corporate strategy by clarifying how cultural orientation shapes competitive outcomes.

Keywords: Cournot duopoly game, corporate social responsibility, customer orientation, linear inverse demand.

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Introduction

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) refers to a business approach that seeks to balance economic goals with social and environmental responsibilities. A socially responsible firm integrates CSR principles into its operations, taking into account environmental, social, and ethical considerations beyond profit. Such firms aim to maximize their own profits together with a share of the consumer surplus. Theoretical economic models incorporating socially responsible firms have been extensively investigated in numerous studies. A brief review of this theoretical literature is provided below.

Research on mixed oligopolies has increasingly emphasized the strategic role of CSR in shaping market outcomes. Kopel & Brand (2012) demonstrate that when a socially responsible firm and a profit-maximizing firm compete over output levels, both firms hire managers in a subgame-perfect Nash equilibrium. Kopel, Lamantia, & Szidarovszky (2014) analyze a mixed Cournot oligopoly with socially responsible and profit-maximizing firms, showing that socially responsible firms can secure larger market shares and higher profits than their profit-maximizing rivals. Their evolutionary approach further reveals that CSR preferences may evolve through profit-driven dynamics, leading to multiple equilibria that depend on the initial conditions and parameters. These findings underscore the importance of dynamic considerations, as evolutionary competition may generate either more or less CSR than static competition.

The choice between price and quantity contracts in mixed oligopolies has also been examined. Nakamura (2013) examines how quantity and price competition affect CSR in a mixed duopoly comprising a socially responsible firm and a profit-maximizing firm and demonstrates that quantity competition yields higher equilibrium CSR levels and greater social efficiency than price competition. Building on this line of research, Kopel (2015) investigates a mixed duopoly with heterogeneous firm objectives, focusing on the endogenous selection between price and quantity contracts. His results indicate that price competition may reduce overall welfare relative to quantity competition, highlighting the welfare implications of strategic contract choice. Similarly, Matsumura & Ogawa (2016) show that asymmetric CSR weights lead firms to prefer Bertrand competition, whereas marginal asymmetry favors Cournot competition.

Dynamic competition and endogenous timing further enrich the analysis of CSR. Fanti & Buccella (2016, 2018) extend this line of research to network industries, demonstrating that sufficiently strong network externalities make CSR-oriented equilibria more profitable than purely profit-maximizing ones, and that joint determination of CSR levels can yield optimal positive CSR. García, Leal, & Lee (2019) develop a quantity-setting duopoly model in which a profit-maximizing firm competes with a socially responsible rival that accounts for environmental externalities and the adoption of clean technology. Allowing firms to choose whether to move first or second, the authors show that equilibrium outcomes vary with parameter values and that a CSR emphasis on consumer surplus can enhance profitability.

The welfare implications of CSR in mixed oligopolies have been widely debated. Using general demand and cost functions, Flores & García (2016) show that when the profit-maximizing firm is technically more efficient, even slight increases in CSR by the rival firm may reduce overall welfare. Their findings highlight that welfare effects depend critically on relative efficiency. Lambertini & Tampieri (2012) provide a contrasting perspective, showing that the presence of at least one socially responsible firm in a pollution-related oligopoly enhances overall welfare. Similarly, Besley & Ghatak (2007) argue that CSR can emerge as an equilibrium outcome when the demand for public goods is sufficiently strong and firms possess market power.

CSR has also been studied in relation to privatization and ownership structures. Han (2019) integrates CSR into a mixed oligopoly framework with partially privatized state-owned enterprises, showing that the equilibrium CSR levels depend on private ownership shares and shareholder preferences. Ouattara (2017) finds that domestic mixed duopolies require lower levels of privatization than international duopolies and suggests that governments reduce privatization as CSR increases. Wang & Wang (2022) further show that CSR influences product quality, profitability, and welfare in vertically differentiated mixed duopolies, contingent on the extent of privatization.

Additional contributions explore CSR in specific industries and contractual environments. Xu (2014) examines hospital duopolies, showing that CSR may raise or lower equilibrium price and quality depending on its intensity and cost structures. Baron (2008) analyzes managerial contracts that encourage CSR, highlighting the role of preference alignment and project observability. Ohnishi (2022) analyzes a mixed duopoly in which a profit-maximizing firm and a socially responsible firm compete in output decisions. In this setting, each firm may adopt a wage-rise contract that ties workers' wages to production levels. Ohnishi (2021) investigates a Cournot oligopoly with nonlinear demand, focusing on socially responsible firms that employ lifetime employment as a strategic commitment and deriving their reaction functions. Extending this analysis, Ohnishi (2023) examines a two-stage Cournot duopoly with concave demand, in which socially responsible firms independently decide whether to commit to lifetime employment, and derives the subgame-perfect equilibrium outcomes.

Taken together, this body of literature demonstrates that CSR significantly shapes firm behavior, market outcomes, and welfare in mixed oligopolies. These findings highlight the importance of dynamic competition, contractual choices, ownership structures, and industry-specific characteristics in determining the equilibrium role of CSR.

This study compares the strategic potential of CSR and CO as commitments in a Cournot competition, modeled as a multi-stage game. I examine whether firms prefer to focus on their own customers (CO) or on all consumers (CSR). CO indicates that firms actively prioritize customer satisfaction, such as offering good service, handling complaints effectively, and making product information accessible. Königstein & Müller (2001) argue that firms can benefit in the long run by caring not only about profits but also about customer welfare, especially in competitive markets. Königstein & Müller (2001) use an indirect evolutionary game-theory model to show that firms that care about their customers' well-being, rather than just their own profits, can gain a

competitive edge in heterogeneous markets. In this model, firms include the consumer surplus in their goals. Although this might reduce short-term profits, it could lead to better long-term outcomes by attracting and retaining customers, especially when competing with purely profit-driven firms. Being customer-oriented can be evolutionarily stable; it helps firms survive and succeed over time, even if it does not always maximize immediate profits.

Planer-Friedrich & Sahm (2018) extend the Cournot duopoly setting proposed by Königstein & Müller (2001) and argue that firms in a Cournot competition benefit more from caring about CSR than from caring only about CO, thereby offering a theoretical explanation for the shift from CO to CSR. The preference for CSR over CO provides a theoretical rationale for the observed shift in corporate culture from customer-centric strategies to broader social responsibility initiatives. CSR can be strategically advantageous. In addition, Ohnishi (2024) examines two Cournot duopoly games in which two profit-maximizing firms produce complementary goods. The initial game assumes that both firms care about CSR as part of their corporate culture, whereas the subsequent game demonstrates that both firms care about CO. Ohnishi shows that the profits in the CSR duopoly solution are equal to those in the CO duopoly solution.

Together, these studies deepen our understanding of how corporate culture interacts with market structure. Planer-Friedrich & Sahm (2018) highlight the strategic advantages of CSR in markets with substitutable goods, whereas Ohnishi (2024) demonstrates that these advantages may vanish when the goods are complementary.

This study compares CO and CSR in a two-stage Cournot game. In the first stage, firms simultaneously and independently choose their corporate culture levels. In the second stage, they select output to maximize their respective objective functions. I derive and present the model's equilibrium outcome.

Planer-Friedrich & Sahm (2018) analyze three duopoly games: competition between two CSR firms, competition between one CSR and one CO firm, and competition between two CO firms, and conclude that CSR generates strategic advantages because it enables firms to achieve higher profits. By contrast, I examine a duopoly game in which each firm independently chooses its corporate culture, specifically CO and CSR, and the equilibrium analysis shows that firms prefer CO because it directly maximizes profits in the Cournot framework. The key difference lies in the strategic environment. While Planer-Friedrich & Sahm (2018) analyze scenarios in which CSR and CO are exogenously given, my model assumes an endogenous cultural choice, leading to different equilibrium outcomes.

Model

Consider a Cournot model with two profit-maximizing firms: firm 1 and firm 2. Throughout this study, I consider neither entry nor exit. Hereafter, subscripts 1 and 2 represent firm 1 and firm 2, respectively. Moreover, when i and j are used to refer to firms in an expression, they should be understood to represent 1 and 2 with $i \neq j$. The production quantity of firm i ($i = 1, 2$) is denoted by q_i . The linear price-demand

function is given by $P = 1 - (q_1 + q_2)$, where P is the market price. Firm i 's cost is given by $q_i^2/2$. These assumptions follow Planer-Friedrich & Sahn (2018).

Therefore, firm i 's profit is given by

$$\pi_i = \left[1 - (q_i + q_j)\right] q_i - \frac{1}{2} q_i^2. \quad (1)$$

I examine whether firms prefer to focus on CO or on CSR. The former represents the surplus of firm i 's customers, denoted by C_i (see, e.g., Königstein & Müller, 2001; Planer-Friedrich & Sahn, 2018), where

$$C_i(q_i, q_j) = \int_0^{q_i} P(x, q_j) dx - P(q_i, q_j) q_i, \quad (2)$$

and the latter represents the surplus of all consumers, denoted by CS (see, e.g., Goering, 2007; Kopel & Brand, 2012; Kopel, Lamantia, & Szidarovszky, 2014; Planer-Friedrich & Sahn, 2018), where

$$CS(q_i, q_j) = \int_0^{q_i+q_j} P(x, y) d(x+y) - P(q_i, q_j)(q_i + q_j). \quad (3)$$

Therefore, firm i 's objective function is given by

$$V_i = \pi_i + \theta_i C_i + (1 - \theta_i) CS = \left[1 - (q_i + q_j)\right] q_i - \frac{1}{2} q_i^2 + \frac{1}{2} \theta_i q_i^2 + \frac{1}{2} (1 - \theta_i) (q_i + q_j)^2, \quad (4)$$

where $\theta \in [0, 1]$ represents the level of corporate culture.

The game's timing is as follows: In the first stage, each firm simultaneously and independently selects its corporate culture level θ_i . In the second stage, each firm simultaneously and independently determines its output level to maximize its objective function V_i . Subgame perfection is adopted as the equilibrium concept. The next section presents the model's equilibrium.

Equilibrium

I solve the game using backward induction to derive the subgame-perfect equilibrium. At the second stage, firm i selects its output q_i to maximize its objective function (4), given the rival's corporate culture level θ_j . The first-order condition $\partial V_i / \partial q_i = 0$ yields firm i 's best response:

$$q_i(q_j) = \frac{1 - \theta_i q_j}{2}. \quad (5)$$

By substituting one reaction function into the other, the equilibrium quantity of firm i is obtained as a function of θ_i and θ_j :

$$q_i = \frac{2 - \theta_i}{4 - \theta_i \theta_j} \quad (6)$$

At stage one, each firm anticipates these quantities and the associated price and selects θ_i to maximize its profit:

$$\pi_i = \frac{2\theta_j(\theta_i - 1)(\theta_i - 2) - (\theta_i - 2)(3\theta_i - 2)}{2(\theta_i \theta_j - 4)^2} \quad (7)$$

From the first-order condition $\partial \pi_i / \partial q_i = 0$ and the symmetry of firms, the equilibrium level of corporate culture is obtained as $\theta_i = \theta = 1$. To compare the equilibrium of this study with that of Planer-Friedrich & Sahn (2018), I assume the symmetry of firms. Thus, firm i chooses to focus on CO. The resulting equilibrium quantities and profits are obtained as $q_i = q \approx 0.3333$ and $\pi_i = \pi \approx 0.0556$, respectively.

The equilibrium outcome of this model can be summarized as follows:

PROPOSITION 1: In equilibrium, firms care only about their own customers (CO).

Proposition 1 indicates that firms focus on CO rather than on CSR. Planer-Friedrich & Sahn (2018) analyze three separate games: competition between two CSR firms, competition between one CSR firm and one CO firm, and competition between two CO firms. They argue that firms in Cournot competition strategically benefit more from caring about CSR than from caring only about CO. In contrast, I analyze a duopoly game in which each firm independently and simultaneously selects the optimal level for its corporate culture, specifically CO and CSR. The contrasting equilibrium outcomes between this study and Planer-Friedrich & Sahn (2018) arise from differences in the modeling approach to firm behavior in Cournot competition.

To elaborate further, Planer-Friedrich & Sahn (2018) analyze three games separately. In the case of competition between two CSR firms, the equilibrium CSR level θ^{SS} is 0.149. The resulting equilibrium profits are obtained as $\pi^{SS} \approx 0.0877$. In the case of competition between one CSR firm and one CO firm, the equilibrium CSR level θ^S is 0.189, and the equilibrium CO level θ^C is 0.289. The resulting equilibrium profits are obtained as $\pi^S \approx 0.0880$ and $\pi^C \approx 0.0857$. In the case of competition between two CO firms, the equilibrium CO level θ^{CC} is 0.382. The resulting equilibrium profits are obtained as $\pi^{CC} \approx 0.0854$. Thus, in the subgame-perfect Nash equilibrium, both firms adopt CSR as their corporate culture.

In this study, firms independently and simultaneously select their corporate culture levels in the first stage of the game. It is impossible for firm i to choose only CSR at 0.149 or only CO at 0.382. As seen in (4), when $\theta_i = 1$, firm i chooses only CO, and when $\theta_i = 0$, firm i chooses only CSR. When $\theta_i \in (0,1)$, firm i chooses both CO and CSR at a constant proportion. When $\theta_i \in [0,1]$, π_i decreases as θ_i decreases. Consequently, firm i achieves greater profits by selecting $\theta_i = 1$.

Discussion

This section presents a welfare analysis and policy implications based on the equilibrium outcome presented in the previous section.

Welfare Analysis

This subsection briefly describes how consumer surplus (CS) and social welfare (W) change as θ varies.

Table 1. Welfare analysis

Θ	q	P	π	CS	W
1	0.3333	0.3333	0.0556	0.2222	0.3333
0.9	0.3448	0.3103	0.0476	0.2378	0.3329
0.8	0.3571	0.2857	0.0383	0.2551	0.3316
0.7	0.3704	0.2593	0.0274	0.2743	0.3292
0.6	0.3846	0.2308	0.0148	0.2959	0.3254
0.5	0.4	0.2	0	0.32	0.32

Table 1 presents a welfare analysis examining the impact of varying levels of θ on W . This table shows that as θ increases, q and CS decrease, while P , π , and W increase. Specifically, when firms prioritize CO entirely (i.e., set $\theta = 1$), welfare is maximized at 0.3333. Moreover, when θ decreases from 1 to 0.5, the welfare value drops from 0.3333 to 0.32. When θ is less than 0.5, π becomes negative. This finding indicates that firms focusing solely on their own customers (CO) achieve higher social welfare than those that attempt to balance CO and CSR.

Policy Implications

The policy implications of this study suggest that firms engaged in Cournot competition naturally prioritize CO over CSR because of its direct profit-maximizing benefits. However, this preference for CO may lead to suboptimal outcomes for overall societal welfare, because CSR initiatives often aim to balance economic goals with social and environmental responsibilities. As shown in Table 1, as θ decreases, π also decreases, but CS increases.

To address this issue, policymakers could consider implementing measures to incentivize CSR adoption. These measures may include tax benefits, subsidies, or regulatory requirements that encourage firms to integrate CSR into their corporate strategies. By doing so, policymakers can help align private business interests with broader societal goals, such as environmental sustainability, social equity, and consumer welfare.

Concluding Remarks

The theoretical analysis by Planer-Friedrich & Sahm (2018) examines three games and concludes that firms in a Cournot competition benefit more from caring about CSR than from focusing solely on CO. Therefore, this study analyzes a Cournot game with two profit-maximizing firms to determine whether firms should prioritize CO or CSR. The results demonstrate that, in equilibrium, firms focus solely on their own customers (CO), favoring CO over CSR. In other words, the equilibrium analysis shows that firms prioritize CO because doing so directly maximizes profits in a one-shot Cournot game. This finding highlights the CO's strategic dominance in quantity-setting competition, in which firms prioritize direct customer relationships to maximize profits.

In this study, I examine a one-shot game with linear inverse demand. Future research could extend the model to heterogeneous markets or dynamic frameworks to explore the conditions under which CSR is strategically viable. Several additional extensions are also worth exploring. First, incorporating asymmetric cost structures between firms can provide insights into how cost differences influence the strategic choice between CO and CSR. Second, analyzing the endogenous choice of corporate culture in a Bertrand competition framework in which firms compete on price rather than quantity, could offer a deeper understanding of the implications for market outcomes and welfare. Finally, explicitly modeling consumer loyalty within the CO objective could shed light on how long-term customer relationships affect firms' strategic decisions and profitability in competitive markets.

Author Contributions

The sole author contributed to all aspects of the study and approved the final manuscript.

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Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Appendix

In the appendix, I calculate the equilibrium level of corporate culture using equation (7). I derive the first-order condition:

$$\frac{\partial \pi_i}{\partial q_i} = (3\theta_j^3 - 12\theta_j^2 + 12\theta_j)\theta_i^2 - (4\theta_j^3 - 4\theta_j^2 - 32\theta_j + 48)\theta_i + 16\theta_j^2 - 64\theta_j + 64 = 0.$$

Since this is a quadratic equation, I solve it by considering two distinct cases.

First, I solve the following equation:

$$\theta_i = \frac{2(\theta_j + 3)(\theta_j - 2)^2 + 2(\theta_j - 3)(\theta_j - 2)^2}{3\theta_j(\theta_j - 2)^2}.$$

This can be simplified as follows:

$$\theta_i = \frac{4\theta_j(\theta_j - 2)^2}{3\theta_j(\theta_j - 2)^2}.$$

Therefore, we obtain $\theta_i = 4/3$.

Second, I consider the following equation:

$$\theta_i = \frac{2(\theta_j + 3)(\theta_j - 2)^2 - 2(\theta_j - 3)(\theta_j - 2)^2}{3\theta_j(\theta_j - 2)^2}.$$

This can be simplified as follows:

$$\theta_i = \frac{4}{\theta_j}.$$

From the symmetry of firms, $\theta_i = \theta = 2, -2$. Since $\theta \in [0,1]$, setting $\theta = 0$ yields $q_i = 1$, $P = -1$, and $\pi_i = -1.5$, which is unrealistic.

From the above discussions and Table 1, the equilibrium level of corporate culture is obtained as $\theta_i = \theta = 1$.

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